

A roadmap to co-create an agroecological vision for the Baltic Sea Region

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Authors:

Michael Löbmann, *Svensk Kolinlagring & Nordic Agroecological Research Centre, Malmö, Sweden*

Anda Ādamsons-Fiskoviča, *Baltic Studies Centre, Riga, Latvia*

Emīls Kīlis, *Baltic Studies Centre, Riga, Latvia*

Eva Āboliņa, *Baltic Studies Centre, Riga, Latvia*

Gabija Pamerneckytė, *Baltic Environmental Forum, Vilnius, Lithuania*

Nina Isabella Moeller, *University of Southern Denmark, Esbjerg, Denmark*

Kaj Granholm, *Baltic Sea Action Group, Helsinki, Finland*

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1. Introduction

Socio-economic disparities, climate change, biodiversity loss, degradation of soils, excessive pollution of our environment globally as well as in the Baltic Sea region, pose significant threats to the stability, wealth and wellbeing of our societies. Soil degradation is a prominent symptom of this development, leading to erosion, reduced water and nutrient holding capacity and increasing pathogen pressure, which in return leads to increased fertiliser and pesticide use as well as their leaching into freshwater bodies and the Baltic Sea (Shokri et al., 2025). Currently, soil degradation contributes to climate change through soil organic carbon losses (IPCC, 2023), although soils could be a carbon sink and thus an important factor for achieving the climate goals of the Paris agreement (Griscom et al., 2017). Dominant agricultural practices and food systems are among the largest contributors to these detrimental developments (Reckermann et al., 2022; Dudley & Alexander, 2017). However, responsibilities do not only lie within primary producers' hands who physically manage the land. Agricultural and food industries, retail and consumers largely shape our current food systems. Thus, all food system stakeholders are setting the frame for farmers' practices together.

Singular adjustments within our food system promise little success for sustainable adjustment (EEA, 2023; IPES-Food, 2016). Without systemic action, resilience and sustainability of our food systems are at risk, jeopardising food security, environmental integrity, and socio-economic stability (FAO, 2021). Further, fragmented policy frameworks and limited stakeholder engagement hinder coordinated efforts for systemic change (EEA, 2023; IPES-Food, 2016).

A sustainable transformation at the food system level is a vital necessity to overcome these complex problems (EEA, 2023; HLPE, 2019). Agroecology emerges as a holistic, stakeholder inclusive problem-solving approach gaining traction in the European Union (EU) and national policies, research and practice (EC, 2020; Wezel et al., 2018). Agroecology relies on solutions that work together with nature rather than against it, while including people's needs, realities and wishes (FAO, 2018). It is a science, practice, and social movement that addresses the challenges of developing an agroecological food system transformation towards true sustainability (Wezel et al., 2009).

The **AE-Pro-Vision project (2024-2025)** - Creating an Action Plan for an Agroecological Baltic Sea Region Vision - financed by the Swedish Institute, aimed to establish a cooperative effort across Baltic Sea region (BSR) countries, engaging stakeholders from various sectors. The consortium consisted of academic, environmental, and farming organisations, catalysing collaborative action and innovation across sectors, national and cultural borders. Through mapping of diverse BSR stakeholders, including farmers, processors, retailers, researchers, policymakers, activists and consumers, the project sparked an inclusive dialogue on how to best develop a joint BSR vision for an agroecological transition.

Here we present the project's final results that outline a methodology for fruitful stakeholder engagement to set the ground for developing a joint BSR vision for an agroecological transformation of our food systems, shaping policies, research and practices for a resilient future. We first outline the overall methodological framework of the AE-Pro-Vision project

(Section 2), with some more comprehensive description of the materials and methods used (Section 3), followed by the presentation of main results (Section 4) stemming from the literature review, stakeholder interviews, and stakeholder workshop, and rounding up with a synthesis (Section 5), and a proposed methodology for co-creating an agroecological vision (Section 6).

While the discussion and conclusions of this report focus on a methodology for co-creating a vision, the report contains a lot of additional information that we did not analyse here. We anyway felt that it is useful to publish these results within this report. We hope to implement this methodology within one or several follow-up projects in order to develop an agroecological vision to unite people and implement transformative change. Of course, we invite everyone to use our results to promote agroecology within their own initiatives.

2. Methodological framework of the AE-Pro-Vision project

The AE-Pro-Vision project is a seed project to set the ground for collaboration around the BSR and to prepare the co-creation of an agroecological vision for the BSR. The idea with the vision is to unite people to co-create and reach common goals, covering the perspectives, needs, realities and wishes of diverse food system stakeholders. Based on such a democratic development process, the vision should help with long-term oriented policy making and provide a long-term goal for practitioners for targeted action, planning and investment security (Borup et al., 2006).

When creating a shared vision, up-front choices in problem framing, assumptions, and proposal design strongly condition the eventual outcomes, which is why visioning and backcasting emphasise early, participatory co-design (Wiek & Iwaniec, 2012; Quist & Vergragt, 2006). In acknowledgement of this, AE-Pro-Vision used the opportunity for early stage stakeholder engagement to support the development of a methodology and method design for the vision co-creation. We chose a four stage process:

1. A brief literature review to cover the most important related previous work and experiences;
2. Targeted interviews with experts in the BSR within the fields of agroecology and sustainable food systems;
3. An international stakeholder workshop in order to get feedback on the results of this exploratory study;
4. The creation and testing of a stakeholder survey questionnaire.

3. Material and Methods

3.1 Literature review

We performed an online search for relevant literature for vision co-creation, with a focus on agroecological, sustainability, or food system transformation. The literature search was conducted in July 2025 using several internationally recognised databases and academic resources, including www.academia.edu, www.researchgate.net, www.sciencedirect.com.

These platforms were used to identify scientific articles, studies, and publications relevant to the topic and objectives of the research. The search process employed the following keywords and their combinations: agroecology vision, foresight analysis, future scenarios, scenario planning, as well as other terms related to the research theme. The keywords were adapted to the specific search functionalities of each database in order to ensure the broadest and most accurate possible selection of relevant literature. In addition to the targeted search, the analysis also included articles and publications suggested by the databases as thematically related to the sources already identified, thereby allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of the subject area. The aim of this effort was to look for existing examples for structured, stakeholder based analysis of food systems to identify current problems and co-design desirable futures. Of particular interest were previously applied methodologies and methods, along with recent frameworks addressing the aggregation or nesting of visions from local to global contexts. Finally, 14 articles were selected for further analysis.

We applied an AI-assisted approach (using ChatGPT (GPT-5.2, OpenAI)) to support the structured analysis of a preselected set of scientific articles. For each article, the AI was prompted to extract (1) the research or study objectives and/or research questions, (2) the applied methodology, including references to additional methods used within the study, and the research questions these methodologies were designed or used to address, and (3) the study abstract. The AI was instructed to report on methods related to the (co-)design of a mutual or shared vision, with a focus on the processes of methodology application, the phases in which these methods were applied, the roles of different stakeholders involved across these phases, and the contexts in which the methods were used.

Following the AI-generated extraction, all 14 articles were revisited by the research team for systematic fact checking against the original publications to verify accuracy, clarify ambiguities, and correct any potential misinterpretations. This validation step ensured that the AI output functioned as an analytical aid rather than a substitute for human interpretation and that all reported information remained faithful to the original sources.

3.2 Expert interviews

We conducted semi-structured expert interviews in Latvia, Lithuania, Sweden, Germany, Denmark and Finland between January and July 2025. For our study, people were regarded as experts if they had a substantial background in agroecology or similar fields (e.g. holistic sustainable development). The experts were interviewed face-to-face or online for about 30-70 minutes, depending on their availability. Generally, three to six experts per country were interviewed (see Table 1), covering diverse sectors (academia, industry, government or civil society representatives), including 13 female and 11 male interviewees. Interviews were audio-recorded for transcription and further analysis. All interview results were anonymised.

The goal of the interviews was to undertake a preliminary mapping of agroecology in the reviewed countries and to collate critical information for the development of a methodology for co-creating a joint BSR vision for agroecology. The interviews followed a guideline document, jointly developed and agreed upon by the project partners (see Appendix 1). The

interview was structured in two main sections: (i) background, definition and status quo of agroecology in the respective country of the interviewee, and (ii) preconditions and potential facilitating and hindering factors for developing a successful vision co-creation process. Additionally, we asked about the relevance of the BSR, target groups, objectives, and a desirable time frame for the vision.

Table 1. Number of experts interviewed per country and primary stakeholder category.

	TOTAL	Research/ Academia	Business/ Industry	NGO/ Civil society	Government/ Public authority
LV	6	2	-	2	2
LT	4	2	1	1	-
SE	5	2	2	1	-
DK	3	-	-	3	-
FI	3	2	1	-	-
DE	3	3	-	-	-
TOTAL	24	12	4	6	2

We synthesised main observations and statements formulated by the experts. Our primary focus was on similarities and differences within and between the respective countries, thus we structured the analysis in two stages: (i) national interview analyses, and (ii) a cross-country comparative analysis.

3.3 Stakeholder Workshop

We held an international stakeholder workshop on 3 October 2025 at the biannual Agroecology Europe Forum in Malmö, Sweden. The workshop lasted for 60 minutes and was open to all participants of the forum (ca. 400 forum attendees). 17 people joined the workshop. During the workshop, we presented the project, its purpose and the results of the expert interviews. Then, participants were asked two questions:

1. Do you see any value in focusing on the BSR for an AE Vision? Which, if any?
2. Who should be involved in the vision building process? How should they be involved?

The questions were discussed openly together with the whole group, so that thoughts and ideas could be debated and progressed by all participants. The workshop was audiorecorded for analysis.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Literature review

Over the years, numerous structured, multi-step methodologies have been developed and tested for co-creating visions for agroecological or sustainable futures. These methodologies differ by the depth of analysis, the types of engagement required, and the comparative importance of diagnosis, visioning, and pathway design. We selected a total of 14 key publications for our analysis (see Appendix 2). Below, we describe seven related key methodologies and discuss their advantages and limitations.

Vision Modeling for Sustainability

The vision modeling methodology of Iwaniec et al. (2014) integrates participatory sustainability visioning with systems-based modeling to support the co-creation of rigorous and practicable sustainability visions. It combines stakeholder articulation of desirable future states with participatory systems modeling, in which stakeholders and experts jointly construct representations of the envisioned future. Thus, the future desirable state is explicitly articulated as a systems model rather than as a narrative or list of goals. Vision modeling is implemented through three interlinked tiers, which may be applied iteratively:

(i) **Conceptual vision modeling** supports stakeholders in jointly mapping vision elements and their relationships using qualitative methods such as causal-loop diagrams, influence matrices, or actor-oriented models. This tier helps identify system structure, dependencies, synergies, trade-offs, and missing or conflicting components.

(ii) **Dynamic modeling** translates selected parts of the conceptual model into parameterised simulation models that allow participants to explore feedback loops, non-linear dynamics, thresholds, and the plausibility of vision goals through scenario testing and visualisation.

(iii) **Pathway modeling** works backward from the envisioned future to the present, enabling participants to identify interventions, policies, and conditions required to achieve the vision and to assess sustainability or reality gaps between current trajectories and desired outcomes.

The strength of this methodology lies in its ability to enhance systems thinking while improving the coherence, plausibility, and tangibility of a co-created vision. By making assumptions and uncertainties explicit and allowing visions to be tested through simulation, vision modeling supports stakeholder negotiation, identification of leverage points, and the development of shared, actionable futures. Empirical applications demonstrate that the approach enables participants to better scrutinise sustainability solutions and, in educational settings, significantly strengthens anticipatory and systems-thinking competencies.

However, vision modeling is resource-intensive and requires skilled facilitation, technical expertise, and sustained stakeholder engagement. Dynamic and pathway modeling may be difficult to access for participants without prior modeling experience, and the approach

depends on data availability and adequate timeframes. Without careful design, there is a risk that complexity may overshadow important processes or limit meaningful participation.

Three Horizons (3H) framework

The Three Horizons framework (Sharpe et al., 2016) provides a straightforward approach that structures and guides dialogue about different patterns of change, as illustrated through practical examples. The approach supports participants in engaging with complex, systemic challenges and uncertain futures. It is particularly valuable for helping groups navigate uncertainty while fostering a sense of agency in a way that many other frameworks do not explicitly address. The Three Horizons framework structures collective reflection into three horizons:

Horizon 1: Business as usual. Identifying current system challenges and elements that must change.

Horizon 2: Transitional activities and innovations. Elaborating innovations and practices for a transition from horizon 1 to horizon 3.

Horizon 3: Desirable long-term futures. Envisaging a stable, new status quo that we want to reach.

The Three Horizons framework supports stakeholders to identify current problems, articulate shared visions, explore tensions between present and future, and design transition pathways. The framework creates a temporal structure that helps participants understand transition dynamics and improves clarity on systemic drivers, leverage points, and required innovations. The co-design approach values diverse knowledge, enabling technical, practical, emotional and cultural inputs and encourages multiple perspectives rather than forcing consensus (Aguiar et al., 2020; Schaal et al., 2023). The confrontation of divergent perspectives helps to address and mitigate conflicts at an early stage, thus increasing success (Collste et al., 2023). Disadvantages of the framework include a potential oversimplification of political dimensions or power relationships. Further, the approach is time-intensive and strongly relies on skilled facilitators in order to ensure good results (Schaal et al., 2023).

TATA-BOX (Designing Territorial Agroecological Transitions)

Similar to Sharpe et al. (2016), Audouin et al. (2019) present the TATA-BOX methodology, a five-step participatory process designed to support territorial agroecological transitions. The approach begins with a holistic diagnosis of the current situation, followed by the development of scenarios that explore external forces likely to influence the territory. Stakeholders then collaboratively co-design a desired Territorial Agroecological System, articulating a shared vision of future agriculture that aligns with local priorities. This visioning stage is complemented by a backcasting process that identifies the steps needed to move from the present to the desired future. Finally, the methodology concludes by defining concrete steps required to steer a successful transition.

The TATA-BOX approach integrates farming systems, supply chains, and natural resource management, enabling a comprehensive territorial perspective. It combines forecasting techniques with normative visioning and structured backcasting, supported by iterative visual tools (e.g. cognitive maps and diagrams) that stimulate innovation and collective reflection. This results in concrete and actionable outcomes, including shared visions, transition pathways, and proposed governance structures.

However, the methodology requires careful coordination among diverse actor groups, as well as readiness from participants to engage in normative debates about desired futures. Significant facilitation is needed to balance creative exploration with practical feasibility and to ensure that the process remains coherent and inclusive throughout its multiple stages (Audouin et al., 2019).

Participatory Co-Design of Farming Systems

Martin et al. (2018) describe a multi-stage, participatory design methodology that integrates farmer knowledge, scientific expertise, and simulation models to support sustainable farming transitions. Stages include comprehensive analysis for problem framing, co-design of innovations, and simulation modeling. It emphasises iterative feedback between stakeholders and models. Martin et al. (2018) combined transition theory, agroecological principles, and farming systems research. They mapped how analytical, participatory, and modelling approaches address specific layers of system complexity. Mixed-method data collection provides a broad perspective, including environmental indicators, farm typologies, structural constraints, and socio-economic drivers. Participatory co-design sessions use prototype farming systems, scenario cards, and multi-criteria discussions. Farmers and advisors iteratively create, assess, and refine alternative systems, making tacit knowledge visible. The previously collected data helps to ground the co-design phase in real life to develop feasible scenarios.

The approach of Martin et al. (2018) focuses on integration of broad knowledge during an iterative co-design phase, thus strengthening both legitimacy and ownership of visions and solutions. Participants can learn by comparing expected vs. observed outcomes and re-apply their knowledge. However, the methodology yields very context-specific results (location-based), rather than allowing to scale, and the proposed iterative cycles are resource and time intensive. The data collection and complementary modelling need to be well integrated into the co-design to avoid unrealistic visions (Martin et al., 2018).

Hybrid Participatory Modelling (IAAS + ComMod)

Barbier et al. (2023) describe a hybrid participatory modelling methodology that brings together Integrated Assessment of Agricultural Systems (IAAS) and Companion Modelling (ComMod). In this approach, IAAS contributes to quantitative and multi-criteria assessments of agricultural systems, while ComMod enables stakeholders to collaboratively construct multi-agent models that reflect their own knowledge, interactions, and decision-making processes. By combining these two approaches, Barbier et al. (2023) integrate robust

quantitative analysis with participatory learning and dialogue. The process increases transparency around model assumptions and logic, and it allows participants to explore how different actors' constraints and priorities interact through model negotiation. In doing so, the methodology helps develop shared visions that are grounded in both experiential knowledge and empirical data.

The approach of Barbier et al. (2023) strengthens mutual understanding and the co-creation of realistic futures by merging technical modelling with stakeholder engagement. However, IAAS components are often highly complex and may be difficult for participants to understand. The hybrid method also requires extensive datasets, significant modelling expertise, and sustained engagement over time. As participation levels can fluctuate across workshops, facilitators must continuously re-engage stakeholders to maintain momentum and ensure that the co-creation process remains inclusive (Barbier et al., 2023).

The Mānoa Mash-up

Pereira et al. (2018) present the Mānoa mash-up methodology, which integrates the Mānoa scenario approach (Schultz, 2015), the Three Horizons framework (Sharpe et al., 2016), futures literacy practices, and seed analysis to develop optimistic and transformative long-term visions. Central to this approach is the identification of “seeds”— existing local innovations that embody alternative values or practices with transformative potential. These seeds serve as concrete starting points for creative scenario-building. Through tools such as storytelling, the Futures Wheel, and imaginative group exercises, participants collaboratively construct richly textured visions of desirable futures grounded in real-world initiatives.

The approach of Pereira et al. (2018) is very good to root visioning in tangible, present-day innovations, preventing the drift into abstract or technocratic futures. Its strong emphasis on creativity, imagination, and emotional engagement allows participants to explore radically different trajectories, while future literacy exercises help shift perspectives from fear-based to possibility-based thinking. By encouraging multiple, divergent visions rather than forcing consensus, the methodology embraces pluralism and nurtures transformative mindsets.

Despite these strengths, without careful facilitation, the resulting visions may become overly imaginative or insufficiently connected to institutional realities. The methodology also relies on highly diverse participant groups and requires substantial time for workshops and creative exploration. Moreover, its imaginative and narrative focus can make integration with conventional policy or planning processes difficult (Pereira et al., 2018).

Transformative Spaces Methodology

Pereira et al. (2020) outline a Transformative Spaces methodology, a flexible assemblage of participatory approaches designed to convene environments where actors can experiment, reframe persistent problems, and collectively explore pathways for systemic change. The process unfolds through five phases: (i) an initial problem definition that surfaces contested understandings and underlying histories, (ii) an operationalisation phase that identifies and

mobilises diverse actors, (iii) a tactical phase focused on selecting and applying appropriate participatory tools, (iv) an outcomes phase assessing changes at individual, collective, and system levels, and finally, (v) a reflection phase that examines learning, power dynamics, and the durability of emerging transformations. The methodology is intentionally adaptive, enabling the creation of “transformative spaces” rather than prescribing a fixed sequence of techniques.

The approach of Pereira et al. (2020) is notable for explicitly engaging with power relations, readiness for change, and ethical considerations, dimensions that are often overlooked. Its methodological flexibility allows facilitators to draw on arts-based practices, Participatory Action Research, narrative inquiry, and systems mapping, ensuring that emotional, experiential, and structural dimensions of transformation are addressed. By fostering relationships and creating room for experimentation, the methodology strengthens long-term agency and supports the emergence of new coalitions and community-driven initiatives.

However, transformative spaces require long-term engagement and are not easily compressed into short project cycles. They demand a deep contextual understanding of local histories, politics, and social dynamics, and the outcomes can be nonlinear or difficult to predict. The approach also depends heavily on skilled facilitation to guide emergent processes rather than relying on predefined structures (Pereira et al., 2020).

4.2 Interview results

The number of interviewees per country allows only for limited representation on a national level. Likewise, the individual interviews also tend to demonstrate the diversity of views among experts within a country, depending on their profile and background. However, we consider the expert status of the interviewees as a merit for representing the national status quo regarding the topic area. Nevertheless, we recommend to the reader to regard the interview results as an overview rather than as representative results on the BSR level and particularly on a national level. Where relevant, we added in brackets the country where specific statements were made by one or more of the national experts.

Definition and status of agroecology

The general understanding of agroecology (AE) is still fragmented, and it is perceived as an ambiguous concept. Experts from all countries described AE in different ways, ranging from a philosophy to a lifestyle for increased biodiversity, inclusion of traditional knowledge, and seasonal, local food (Lithuania), organic or “uncertified organic” farming based on minimal reliance on industrial inputs (Latvia), or a broad umbrella encompassing regenerative, conservation, organic, permaculture, and other sustainable practices (Denmark, Sweden). For some, it was primarily a branch of ecological science exploring human-agroecosystem interactions (Latvia, Lithuania, Germany), while others framed it as a holistic methodology for food system transformation that integrates social movements, food sovereignty, and democratic decision-making (Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Latvia). In Denmark and Finland,

several interviewees also emphasised the importance of context, location specific approaches with a strong focus on soil health and ecosystem regeneration. In these two countries, respondents perceived agroecology as part of broader, multi-scale landscape management, extending to marine ecosystems, and connecting farming with environmental stewardship.

Experts emphasised the low use of the term 'Agroecology' both in public and among professionals. Further, no consistent understanding prevails beyond expert communities (Latvia, Denmark, Lithuania, Sweden, Germany). However, practitioners are sometimes implementing agroecological practices, without labelling them as such. In Latvia, an interviewee explained that the term AE has been introduced gradually through European policies, but remains poorly understood, particularly within the policy sector, which views it with scepticism due to a perceived vague definition. In all countries, commonly used terms associated with AE include sustainable farming, environmentally friendly farming, organic agriculture, permaculture, regenerative farming, or similar approaches. However, in Denmark, an interviewee reported a growing concern about the co-optation of "regenerative agriculture" by large corporations (e.g., Carlsberg), that might be pushing more people toward adopting the agroecology term instead.

In countries like Sweden and Germany, interviewees argued that AE is currently more rooted within research, where it is understood both as a scientific methodology and as a holistic, transdisciplinary practice. They stressed its multi-level nature, its role for building new consumer-producer relationships, and for transforming governance systems. In Denmark, agroecology – as a holistic approach to food systems transformation – remains marginal in the scientific and academic mainstream, although some research efforts are underway. In Lithuania, a respondent argued that agroecology is understood more as a science, whereas in the EU it is often seen as a practice. This different understanding leads to different views between stakeholders with mistrust and confrontation between scientists and practitioners.

Generally, interviewees indicated increased project funding and an emerging scientific community for agroecology. However, the framing happens often under terms like 'transdisciplinary'. Also, some farmer-to-farmer knowledge exchange on AE takes place under university-led projects. In contrast, while agroecology is mostly understood as a science in Latvia and Lithuania, there is no mention of expanding research or growth in institutionally funded projects there, despite EU-level funding schemes such as the Horizon Europe Soil Mission and the Agroecology Partnership, the latter currently (status: January 2026) does not include Latvia and Poland (not part of this study).

In most countries (Sweden, Germany, Latvia, Denmark, and Finland), some agroecological principles are applied in practice often under the umbrella of organic, or regenerative farming. In Lithuania, interviewees argued that farmers face numerous restrictions and overly strict standards, such as stringent regulations, taxes, and frequent inspections, which leave little room to implement innovative agroecological practices and cause many to disengage from farming altogether. Similarly, Latvian experts argued that, although some organic farmers might identify themselves with agroecology, most farmers are not ready to change their practices, mostly due to economic concerns.

Agroecology as a social movement remains weak and fragmented in Sweden, Germany, Finland and Latvia, where it tends to be limited to small, localised networks such as community supported agriculture (CSA), or seed sovereignty initiatives. In Latvia, there is little to no political mobilisation or social activism around AE. Denmark shows signs of a growing movement, with activist farmers, new entrants, and independent schools (such as the Regenerative Agriculture School) playing an important role. However, the movement remains marginal and lacks political support.

Interest in agroecological topics is growing among youth and students, especially in Germany and Sweden, and environmental and food awareness is on the rise in Finland and Latvia. Latvian respondents emphasised that climate change offers both risks and opportunities for agricultural adaptation, including the introduction of new crops and integration with sectors like tourism, but also societal mobilisation. In Finland, a renewed interest in rural living is also helping to reconnect people with local food systems and nature. In Denmark, experts stressed that the AE movement and the awareness of food system challenges is increasing, supported by different drivers such as the climate movement, media coverage, and events hosted by national institutions like the Kalø Organic College. However, cultural barriers persist. In Latvia, scepticism toward top-down initiatives is common, particularly in rural areas, while in Finland, food-related engagement is often shaped by lifestyle trends, which can obscure the links to primary production.

Collaboration and networks

According to the interviewed experts, collaboration around agroecology is growing, but remains limited and fragmented in each country. In Lithuania, the scientific community is increasingly working on agroecology-related topics, and some individuals are taking up agroecological practices. However, there are few to no bridges between agroecological science and practice. Lithuanian respondents stressed the need for dedicated local institutions to create and support short food supply chains, as well as non-governmental organisations (NGOs) that could unite diverse actors in the field. The Swedish AE movement is reported as fragmented and still weak, even if some clusters exist among farmer unions, local food councils, and vocational schools, with small-scale farmers often collaborating informally. Germany has more formalised structures for AE-oriented collaborations such as community-supported agriculture, environmental NGOs, organic farming groups, and small farmers' associations. However, German respondents reported that the agroecology movement is still weak (yet growing), mainly linked to local networks and consumer initiatives.

Denmark hosts an existing network of organisations alongside educational institutions. Respondents noted that, while these actors already collaborate to some extent and the agroecology movement is actively growing, much more could be done to strengthen connections across different strands of the sustainable farming movement. In particular, taking the example of the Danish 'green tripartite agreement' (which aims to cut carbon from agriculture and restore nature), one interviewee stressed that local participation in implementation processes is limited, and there is little diversity among participants. Similarly,

Latvian respondents emphasised the lack of participatory, bottom-up engagement in local ecological decision-making, leading to a perception of top-down imposition and, consequently, resistance from concerned stakeholders.

Despite these challenges, some promising trends are emerging. In Sweden, municipal involvement and the development of local food strategies offer a more supportive environment for agroecological approaches. In Denmark, farmer-to-farmer exchange and grassroots collaborations are beginning to create more inclusive spaces for agroecological development. In Finland, pioneer farms serve as important examples of agroecological innovation, while inclusive stakeholder engagement supports the integration of AE principles. Some stakeholder mobilisation in Latvia around AE ideas has been done by the Latvian Association of Organic Agriculture, the Permaculture society, as well as the recently launched initiative of the Bioregion of the Gauja National Park.

Policies and institutional context

There is a growing policy interest in agroecology in Sweden, Germany, and Finland, primarily driven by EU research funding and mechanisms within the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). In Latvia, agroecology gained some visibility during the 2015 EU presidency and through alignment with EU policies, but national level understanding of this holistic approach remains limited. In Lithuania, there is little indication of supportive policy structures. Instead, regulatory systems and inspections are often seen as obstacles to the application of AE principles in farming. In Denmark, there is no national political support for agroecology, although organic farming has received policy backing.

Agroecology is still far from being mainstreamed in the political discourse in all of the analysed countries. In Denmark and Lithuania, agroecology was reported to be absent from national strategies and political debates with a strong structural support for industrial agriculture instead. In Latvia, AE has recently been institutionalised in the form of the Department of Climate Change and Agroecology formed within the Ministry of Agriculture, along with a dedicated eco-scheme “Agroecology practices on organic farms”. Yet, in the policy context, the AE concept is generally viewed as too vague or redundant in relation to existing sustainability frameworks. As a result, although the term is used at the EU level and there is growing institutional interest in Sweden, Germany, Finland, and Latvia, national policy frameworks generally do not position agroecology as a central concept. Instead, other sustainability measures, such as support for organic farming or individual eco-schemes, are more widely adopted.

Furthermore, respondents identified a range of policy barriers and opportunities that shape the potential for agroecological transitions, highlighting both the strengths and limitations of existing frameworks. The first observation is that farmers are often hesitant to adopt sustainable practices when they are associated with lower economic returns or increased administrative burdens. Indeed, in Latvia, Lithuania and Denmark, interviewed experts underlined that farmers are already facing major financial difficulties. Therefore, the funding support for farming through the CAP is flagged as an essential factor in need for reforms (Denmark, Sweden, Germany). A Swedish respondent advocated for a reform on how CAP

funds are allocated, while a Danish respondent suggested that a lot of money could be moved towards sustainable practices. An expert from Germany indicated that the CAP provides valuable tools to support agroecology, but is hindered by weak national implementation, while another German respondent argued that the CAP direct payments might contribute to maintaining the status quo rather than promoting agroecology. Finally, a Swedish respondent underlined weaknesses of the CAP regulations, while another emphasised the contradictions between EU policies such as CAP and “Farm to Fork”.

Bureaucratic rigidity and complex policy frameworks continue to discourage innovation and slow down transitions, as underlined in Finland, Latvia, Lithuania, and Germany. True cost accounting was proposed as a solution for policy development, since it would shift the burden of proof e.g. from organic to non-organic practices.

Economic and market constraints

Lithuanian and Danish interviewees reported a lack of infrastructure for direct sales (i.e. direct producer-consumer exchange), and farmers often lack the time, resources, and support needed to access or develop new markets. In Latvia, economic viability remains a key concern. In Denmark and Latvia, respondents put forward the debt constraints faced by farmers, which lock them into a productivist mode of farming. Additionally, a Danish respondent indicated that it is very difficult for young generations, which are generally more open to AE, to access land. A Finnish respondent stressed a lack of agroecological on-farm investments due to the difficulty of accessing loans, as banks put very stringent conditions, which are ill-suited to agroecological practices.

In Germany, Denmark, and Sweden, established market structures and the dominance of industrial agriculture pose major barriers to the broader adoption of agroecology. In Finland, the emphasis on export-oriented agriculture and fragmented food supply chains further hinder incentives for AE-oriented food system transformations. A Danish expert put forward a mismatch between food prices and wages, making it difficult to sustain agroecological models. In Latvia, it was noted that large farms focus mainly on ‘numbers’ (i.e. economic and quantitative factors) than on functions and impact, which undermines functional diversity and structural resilience. Land consolidation and farm enlargement are viewed as obstacles for organic and sustainable farming development. Generally, farmers are unlikely to adopt agroecological practices if these are perceived to reduce or even jeopardise their income.

In Germany, Sweden, and Latvia, respondents reported a lack of adequate advisory systems to support farmers in transitioning to and applying agroecological practices. In Lithuania and Denmark, experts stressed the need for improved commercialisation pathways and better consumer access to agroecological products.

In short, across all countries, economic and market constraints remain significant challenges. The dominance of industrial agriculture, combined with limited advisory support and weak market access for smaller farms continues to hinder both economic and practical viability and expansion of agroecological models.

Structural barriers

The interviewed experts argued that an agroecological transformation faces major structural and systemic constraints across all countries. Indeed, dominant industrial agri-food models and ongoing reliance on fossil fuels were stressed as major factors undermining the viability of agroecological approaches. Likewise, agroecology is frequently misperceived as small-scale, anti-innovation, or impractical, especially among established, conventional sectors in Germany, Sweden, and Latvia.

A Latvian respondent put forward the idea of a lock-in regarding the dominant industrial farming system due to resource availability and cheap fossil fuel prices, making it difficult for agroecological farms to compete with conventional farms. Similarly, in Denmark, structural barriers are particularly developed: the farming sector is heavily dominated by industrial livestock production and import-export-driven production chains. The importance of the dairy sector in the Baltic region is also seen as a potential barrier by one of the Swedish experts. Similarly, Finland has an export-dominated economy, which, if favouring quantity over quality, risks being a major obstacle to AE transition.

A Danish respondent mentioned the lack of educational infrastructure for agroecology and difficulties in land access for young farmers. Swedish and German respondents also stressed the lack of support for young farmers, indicating that generational renewal in agriculture remains uncertain. At the policy level, Swedish respondents highlighted contradictions within EU policies (e.g., CAP vs. “Farm to Fork”), advocating instead for reforming public procurement laws to better support local and regional food systems and encouraging more aspirational policies that support innovation rather than just auditing compliance. Recognising agroecological farming as a viable and secure investment for banks and insurance companies is also deemed as an important barrier to overcome.

Finally, in Latvia and Finland, scepticism of conventional farmers towards symbolically charged terms such as “agroecology” or practices such as “organic farming” present additional hurdles. Public disengagement or limited understanding of farming realities also undermine support for more systemic shifts (Latvia). Generally, creating trust between all actors is a major challenge, yet a crucial factor needed for success.

The relevance of focusing on the BSR

Our interviewees recognised the Baltic Sea Region as a relevant space for testing an international agroecological collaboration, although countries across the region perceived its significance in different ways. Experts in Sweden, Latvia, and Germany emphasised shared environmental challenges like eutrophication and pollution of the Baltic Sea, which are common problems that require coordinated action. Lithuanian and Latvian interviewees highlighted geographical and climatic similarities, particularly among the Baltic countries, where farming practices, food traditions, and cultural values are more aligned. Finish respondents added that social structures across the region are sufficiently similar to allow for the relatively easy replication of agroecological elements and underlined the good

connectivity of the region. In Denmark, however, most experts did not feel a strong affiliation with the BSR. Instead, they felt more connected to the Scandinavian or Nordic countries with clearer similarities in agriculture and policy. Generally, there are three more specific clusters considered in the context of BSR - (i) the Scandinavian/Nordic countries, (ii) the Baltic countries, and (iii) the central European countries, i.e. here Germany.

A Swedish respondent put forward the diversity in agricultural, social, and economic structures across the BSR countries. Similarly, a Lithuanian respondent underlined the similarities between Baltic countries but stressed that context and food cultures are very different between the BSR countries. However, in Germany, Latvia, and Lithuania, interviewees emphasised that the diversity of farming systems and characteristics of each region offer opportunities for mutual learning, as long as strategies remain flexible and adapted to specific national and local contexts. Overall, the BSR was viewed as a promising region for building a collaborative, resilient, and sustainable agroecological future.

Stakeholder engagement and target groups

There was widespread agreement on the importance of involving a broad range of stakeholders in an agroecological transformation. Farmers, particularly young, organic, and regenerative farmers, are consistently identified as a central target group across all countries. According to Danish experts, small-scale farmers are often excluded from key stakeholder dialogues, and neither they nor their organisations get involved in policy development. Therefore, a vision must explicitly include them, aiming at improving their overall situation. Latvian respondents particularly emphasised inclusiveness, stressing the need to involve stakeholders who are often marginalised, such as small-scale market sellers and land managers. Danish respondents stressed that the vision should integrate the most diverse array of people possible and be targeted towards ordinary people to bring in new perspectives, notably through the “critical yeast” perspective (connecting with local individuals who can catalyse wider movement growth) (Lederach, 2005). Experts in Germany emphasised that all AE pillars (i.e. science, movement, and practice) must be present in the vision, with proactive involvement of local actors from the very start. This includes ensuring that farmers are represented not just as recipients but as co-designers of the visioning process.

Participation of local, national, and EU level policy makers was also considered crucial by interviewees from all countries, given their influence and impact on food system regulations, subsidies, and education. Danish respondents stressed that the agroecological vision needs to be accessible to municipalities and local councils, not only farmers, and must be locally anchored in order to have real impact. Civil society actors (including consumers, community organisers, journalists, NGOs, activists, etc.) were also viewed as having a strong role in shaping food cultures and supporting bottom-up change in Sweden, Germany, and Latvia. A Finnish respondent argued that citizens and consumers should be seen as the key audience for the agroecological vision, with taste and sensory experiences acting as an entry point to connect them to agriculture and food. Lithuanian experts emphasised the need for an NGO

or similar structures to bring together different initiatives. Finally, education was particularly emphasised in Lithuania and Latvia, where universities, schools, and even early childhood education are seen as essential for building a sound AE knowledge base and to foster related values at a society level.

Timeframes of the vision

Interviewees formulated the need for a time horizon of the vision that includes near-, medium-, and long-term actions and results. Short-term timeframes of one to five years are seen as crucial for building momentum and generating visible impact through quick wins. Medium-term horizons of five to 15 years are viewed as the ideal window for deeper policy alignment and structural transformations (Latvian respondents proposed a 10–12-year timeline). Long-term vision elements extending to 2050 and beyond are important to frame agroecology within broader climate and sustainability commitments, and to signal the depth and scope of required systemic transformations. Danish respondents emphasised the urgency of immediate action, suggesting that in addition to a long-term vision, shorter-term formats aligned with political cycles, e.g. 4-year or 10-year visions, may be more effective for driving policy changes and public support.

Methodologies and approaches

While differing in details, respondents shared the objective of transforming food systems to become more sustainable, just, resilient, and locally grounded. Agroecology is seen as a holistic transition, reconnecting food production with natural cycles and cultural practices, while balancing social, ecological, and economic needs (Latvia, Lithuania, Germany, Sweden). Priorities such as soil health, biodiversity, food sovereignty, circularity, and the economic viability of rural areas were consistently highlighted.

Education and awareness-building were viewed as critical levers for transformation. Additionally, Lithuanian respondents particularly emphasised the importance of building trust between farmers, consumers and other actors. German and Swedish respondents stressed the importance of aligning agroecological transitions with long-term policy goals and broader societal values. Swedish experts framed the vision as a societal vision, not only an agricultural one, thus linking health, welfare, and environmental goals, while avoiding siloed approaches. The approach needs to be explicitly value-based and normative, addressing food and seed sovereignty, ecosystem health, and social inclusion, while ensuring practical, achievable milestones.

Danish respondents proposed envisioning a new food-producing landscape that balances food production with dedicated nature areas, complemented by a "sea and land" perspective. They also underlined the importance of small farms in building local communities and the need for regional hubs, such as seed networks, to support collaboration and mutual learning. Finnish experts advocated for the development of a 'Common Food Value Chain Policy' to align subsidies with the delivery of public goods,

reinventing the value of leys for multiple uses, and piloting rural settlement programmes for agroecologists to strengthen communities while preventing marginalisation. They emphasised that funding should support movements and networks themselves, not just isolated projects.

There was a strong alignment around the use of participatory, iterative, and locally rooted methods to develop an agroecological vision. Piloting small-scale initiatives before wider implementation was encouraged, as it allows for learning and adaptation. In Sweden, Germany, and Latvia, interviewed experts advocated for bottom-up processes such as living labs, citizen assemblies, and multi-stakeholder platforms, ensuring that diverse perspectives (especially from rural communities) are represented in the decision-making process.

A German respondent outlined a process starting with actor mapping and spatial scoping, followed by participatory visioning exercises and scenario workshops to explore desired futures for farming and food systems. These sessions should bring all stakeholders together at key moments, working backwards from shared visions to identify concrete actions. Similarly, a Latvian respondent introduced the idea of collaborative spatial planning as a means of engaging rural communities and embedding change in place-based contexts.

Danish contributions added that practical approaches should consider what participants gain from engagement, e.g. education, networking, or financial advantages (especially for farmers). Respondents argued that paying for participation can make participation more feasible for a wider range of stakeholders such as farmers. One respondent proposed to experiment with “bioweaving” methods, where diverse actors co-develop strategies through facilitated ‘weaving’ of ideas and knowledge. Swedish experts placed additional focus on storytelling, media engagement, and showcasing successfully implemented AE cases as a way to build trust and momentum. A Danish expert also underlined that the way of communicating the vision is important, and suggested short videos, visuals, and engaging formats to reach a broader audience.

Across the interviews, a set of nine principles emerged for how an agroecological vision should be designed, communicated, and implemented:

1. Holistic scope: Addressing all agroecological dimensions (science, movement, and practice), while connecting food systems to health, well-being, welfare, environment, and community.
2. Inclusive co-design: Defining the scope and content together with a diverse mix of stakeholders to avoid blind spots, using methods like citizen assemblies to build a shared ownership.
3. Bottom-up approach with local focus: Supporting and harnessing activities of local actors and initiatives. Grounding the vision in place-specific realities, with regional hubs and networks, ensuring that the vision operates from the local to the international level, connecting municipal and regional action to national and EU frameworks.
4. Catalytic participation: Identifying and engaging key individuals who can act as multipliers/ambassadors of an AE vision and transformation in their communities.

5. Accessibility & communication: Using engaging formats (videos, images, storytelling, simple language) and building on media presence to reach and connect diverse audiences, from policymakers to ordinary citizens.
6. Value for participants: Ensuring that participants (e.g. small-scale farmers) benefit tangibly, whether through education, networking, or reimbursement.
7. Solidarity & connection: Linking local visions to broader regional and international movements for food and seed sovereignty, climate justice, and ecological resilience.
8. Demonstration & learning: Facilitating practical implementation of the vision through pilot programmes. Developing visible, medium-scale lighthouses to showcase agroecological viability and inspire replication.
9. Follow-through: Avoiding a “project drop-off” by designing a vision for long-term continuity beyond funding cycles.

4.3 Stakeholder workshop

The workshop discussions revealed both strong enthusiasm and significant complexity surrounding the development of a shared agroecological vision for the Baltic Sea Region. Participants widely agreed on the value of a long-term, strategic vision that could guide future policies and local initiatives, while also expressing a need to clarify the purpose, boundaries, and scope of such an endeavour. The facilitators emphasised that the AE-Pro-Vision initiative is intentionally designed as an early-stage, participatory “seed project”, gathering stakeholder insights before any direction is set. This was important in light of questions about whether the initiative had emerged bottom-up or was primarily research-driven.

Participants raised important questions about what constitutes the BSR in practice. An important comment of one participant emphasised the concern that agroecology and a related vision cannot solely be determined by administrative borders. Similarly, the presence of existing regional frameworks such as HELCOM was seen as a major opportunity for coordination, knowledge exchange, and shared learning. Several contributors noted that the BSR could become a meaningful platform for regional identity-building and cross-country alignment, offering both internal benefits and external visibility. This extended to the suggestion that highlighting the BSR’s common environmental, social, and economic challenges could strengthen its voice in European agroecological debates.

A key result of the discussion was the consensus that a BSR’s agroecological vision should not solely focus on farming practices but must instead adopt a broader food system perspective. Participants emphasised that agroecology in the BSR should address community wellbeing, marine ecosystem health, food markets, and human-nature reconnections. For some, agroecology also meant imagining a sea full of fish, vibrant local markets, and stronger social ties. This reinforces the methodological requirement for visioning tools that capture emotions, lived experiences, and cultural values - approaches that go beyond a focus on technological innovation or primary production.

The workshop highlighted the need for a participatory methodology that can integrate a wide range of actors across the food system. It became clear that the process should involve

not only farmers, researchers, and NGOs, but also food processors, financial institutions, media, educators, and even actors typically perceived as peripheral, such as insurance companies or rural newsletters. Importantly, participants stressed that farmers should be reimbursed for their participation to acknowledge their expertise and ensure their involvement. Creative engagement methods such as food festivals, competitions, films, or collaborations with food influencers were presented as effective ways to mobilise citizens and to identify actors beyond formal networks. These methods may be particularly valuable in contexts where agroecology is still relatively unknown.

Despite these opportunities, several barriers were identified. Awareness and understanding of food system related sustainability matters remain uneven and fragmented across the BSR, and cultural, historical, and structural differences between countries may complicate the development of a shared narrative. For instance, farm structures and political contexts vary significantly, creating diverse entry points and challenges. Institutional resistance, particularly from conventional agricultural sectors and regulatory bodies, was also noted as a potential obstacle. Involving large agrifood corporations in the process may be necessary at some stage, but workshop participants cautioned against engaging them too early, due to a potential threat of them diluting the underlying transformative ambition of the vision.

Participants also drew attention to the discrepancy between short project cycles and the long-term nature of political change. Policymakers are more likely to engage with proposals that align with existing mandates or ongoing debates, such as food system preparedness, the sustainable development goals (SDGs), or EU frameworks. Therefore, the vision must be articulated clearly and in a usable form so that NGOs and advocates can employ it in lobbying and public engagement. Several participants suggested that strong public mobilisation, e.g. through citizen campaigns or petitions, could help bring agroecology onto political agendas, as illustrated by experiences from Germany and Norway. However, others noted that researchers often struggle to communicate clearly and need support to produce crisp, accessible messages that can be picked up by civil society.

Despite these hurdles, numerous facilitating factors for implementation emerged from the discussion. Existing regional collaboration platforms, strong interest from NGOs in a unifying vision, public attachment to well-known local issues (like the polluted Oslo fjord), and the interest of unconventional allies (such as banks or insurance companies) may all help build momentum. Participants also noted the potential for cross-border inspiration and positive competition, using pilot farms, successful transitions, and community events to mobilise broader participation.

Overall, the workshop discussion suggested that a successful co-development process for a BSR's agroecological vision must be iterative, inclusive, and grounded in both socio-ecological realities and institutional contexts. It must navigate diverse agricultural systems and food systems, different levels of public awareness, and complex political landscapes, while simultaneously building shared visions that resonate across local and national boundaries. The process will require methodological pluralism, skilled facilitation, and alignment with existing policy debates. Yet, if carefully designed, it has the potential to generate a powerful narrative capable of guiding transformation, strengthening regional and cross-regional

collaboration, and mobilising a wide range of actors toward a more sustainable and just agroecological future for the Baltic Sea Region.

5. Combining the results of desk research, interviews and workshop

The findings from the literature review, expert interviews, and stakeholder workshop converge on a clear message: co-creating an agroecological vision for the Baltic Sea Region is both needed and inherently complex. The process must confront fragmented understandings of agroecology, diverse agricultural and food system structures, varying levels of public awareness, and entrenched political and economic lock-ins. Yet, it also benefits from a strong foundation of shared environmental challenges, emerging networks, growing youth interest, and a desire among many actors to collaborate across borders.

Throughout the AE-Pro-Vision project, several hindering factors for developing a joint BSR vision for agroecology stood out. Conceptual ambiguity around agroecology (e.g. its boundaries, values, practices, and competing interests) may create confusion and miscommunication both within and between BSR countries. Industrialised agri-food structures dominate markets and policy priorities, leaving little flexibility for experimentation. Farmers face economic precarity, debt, limited advisory support, and heavy administrative burdens, which may restrict their interest or ability to explore alternative practices. Public understanding of agroecology is limited, and the movement remains fragmented across the region. Finally, political and bureaucratic dynamics, including contradictions between EU-level and national frameworks, undermines systemic change. These intertwined barriers emphasise that co-creating a vision requires explicit attention to power dynamics, institutional constraints, communication barriers, and uneven capacities for participation.

Important drivers for developing a joint vision are represented by environmental pressures such as eutrophication of the Baltic Sea, which creates a sense of common purpose, while cultural similarities, especially among the Baltic and Nordic countries, offer a basis for learning and cooperation. Activism, municipal food strategy initiatives, grassroots farming networks, and creative community-based engagement are emerging as drivers for agroecology. The desire for cross-border collaboration was evident among interviewees and workshop participants, who saw value in a shared regional narrative that could strengthen advocacy, improve institutional coordination, and highlight BSR-specific challenges and opportunities. Trust-building between farmers and consumers, growing interest in rural living, and the existence of pioneering AE farms also create fertile ground for a regional vision. These opportunities demonstrate that a collective process grounded in shared values, concrete examples, and inclusive collaboration can provide political momentum and legitimacy.

Agroecology is understood as a holistic approach, extending beyond primary production to food culture, community wellbeing, ecosystem restoration, and social justice (Francis et al., 2003). Stakeholders across the region repeatedly underlined that a BSR vision must adopt a

whole-food-system perspective rather than limiting itself to farm-level practices. Participatory and inclusive co-creation is essential but challenging. Both interviews and the workshop pointed to the need to involve a broad spectrum of actors, including farmers, scientists, NGOs, processors, financiers, educators, citizens, while carefully managing power dynamics. Literature on participatory co-design (Martin et al., 2018) and hybrid modelling (Barbier et al., 2023) supports this, demonstrating that legitimacy and ownership arise from iterative, multi-actor engagement, but also that such processes require time, resources, skilled facilitation, and continuous re-engagement.

There is widespread recognition that narratives, values, and emotional engagement matter. Workshop participants spoke of agroecology as a vision for a sea full of fish, stronger communities, and vibrant local markets, echoing the literature's emphasis on imagination, creativity, and storytelling (e.g. Pereira et al., 2018; Schaal et al., 2023; Martin et al., 2018; Aguiar et al., 2020). Across interviews and the workshop, the importance of context-specific solutions was emphasised. In recognition of this, methodologies must be flexible, allowing for place-based adaptation rather than imposing a uniform template (Pereira et al., 2020).

Finally, actors across the region emphasised the need for long-term orientation combined with short-term momentum. Experts called for multi-phase time horizons (short-term pilot actions, mid-term policy alignment, and long-term structural transformation).

Based on the results of the AE-Pro-Vision project, intensive co-creation is the vital backbone of a suitable methodology. The co-created knowledge can be supported and complemented with hard scientific methods in iterative application cycles with stakeholder activities. This can underline the vision's evidence-based character, support its legitimacy even beyond peoples' support, and avoid moving away from achievable scenarios. While such a mixed method approach is useful, it is expensive and time consuming (Martin et al., 2018).

The 3 Horizon approach of Sharpe et al. (2016) provides a good starting point by separating the vision into the 'present state', a 'desired state', and the 'pathway to get there'. Both the TATA-BOX approach (Audouin et al., 2019) and the Transformative Spaces (Pereira et al., 2020) further elaborated this approach, adding more detailed steps. Comparing the latter two methodologies (Table 2), we identified six steps that should be followed for a successful methodology.

Initially, (1) a problem identification phase is needed in order to create common ground amongst stakeholders regarding the problem situation. Then it is necessary to (2) assess the underlying conditions, including which (additional) stakeholders need to be included and which power relations, internal and external factors need to be considered. Based on these preconditions, (3) methods can be selected for the following process of (4) vision co-creation. The vision co-creation methods should then go through interactive (5) reflection cycles in order to test, refine, and improve the vision. Finally, the vision can be (6) concretised through co-developing concrete actions and steps to follow up on the vision, fostering its implementation in policies and practice. We found that the 'Seed' concept presented by Pereira et al. (2018) provides a good starting point for action, especially when addressing large territories such as the BSR.

Table 2. Analytical comparison of the vision creation working steps according to the methodologies of Audouin et al. (2019) and Pereira et al. (2020).

	TATA-BOX	Transformative Spaces
	<i>Audouin et al. (2019)</i>	<i>Pereira et al. (2020)</i>
1. Problem identification	[1] Holistic diagnosis of the current situation.	[1] Initial problem definition.
2. Assessment of conditions	[2] Development of scenarios that explore external forces likely to influence the territory.	[2] Operationalisation phase that identifies and mobilises diverse actors.
3. Method selection		[3] Tactical phase focused on selecting and applying appropriate participatory tools.
4. Vision co-creation	[3] Co-design of a desired Territorial Agroecological System, articulating a shared vision of future agriculture that aligns with local priorities.	[4] [Envisaged?] Outcomes phase assessing changes at individual, collective, and system levels.
5. Reflection and adjustment	[4] Backcasting process that identifies the steps needed to move from the present to the desired future.	[5] Reflection phase that examines learning, power dynamics, and the durability of emerging transformations.
6. Concretisation	[5] Definition of concrete steps required to steer a successful transition.	

Through the AE-Pro-Vision project, we could identify many vital elements needed for a successful vision creation methodology and shed light on each element from different perspectives. Inclusive co-creating is both a requirement and an inherently complex challenge for developing an agroecological vision for the BSR. Strong focus needs to be laid on co-creation design and facilitation. While the co-creation needs to cover a broad spectrum of actors, there is a need for explicit focus on power dynamics, institutional constraints, communication barriers, and uneven capacities for participation (e.g. researchers vs. practitioners) in order to ensure inclusive collaboration. Central outcomes of the vision building process should be shared values that cut across stakeholder groups, and concrete examples to make the results tangible. Political momentum, legitimacy, and a broad public ownership feeling can be achieved through sound stakeholder engagement paired with a supporting evidence base (Martin et al., 2018; Barbier et al., 2023).

Through the literature, we could identify six important steps that are needed for successful co-creation of a vision: (i) Problem identification, (ii) Assessment of underlying conditions, (iii) Method selection, (iv) Vision co-creation, (v) Reflection, and (vi) Concretisation. ‘Problem identification’ and ‘Assessment of conditions’ benefit well from scientific evidence-based support in exchange with stakeholder feedback, while this process can be repeated in iterative cycles of the later stages, i.e. ‘Vision co-creation’ and ‘Reflection’. Finally, scientific evidence helps to solidify the ‘Concretisation’ of co-created results.

Since the creation of a future vision goes beyond our everyday experiences, the methodology needs to employ and foster participants’ imagination and creativity, resulting in inspiring stories and concrete examples (e.g. Pereira et al., 2018; Schaal et al., 2023; Martin et al., 2018; Aguiar et al., 2020). Thus, the methodology needs to embrace the inclusion of narratives, values, and emotional engagement.

Further, a vision co-creation methodology needs to find a balance between a whole-food-system perspective and context-specific solutions on diverse scales (BSR, national local, etc.). Thus, the methodology needs to provide structure, while being flexible enough in some parts to allow local adaptations to avoid imposing uniform templates with low practical relevance (Pereira et al., 2020). Finally, the methodology needs to result in a combination of long-term orientation and short-term momentum through a multi-phase time horizon (short-term pilot actions, mid-term policy alignment, and long-term structural transformation).

6. A Methodology for Co-Creating an Agroecological Vision

In the following we describe an idealised methodology for creating an agroecological vision for the Baltic Sea Region. Idealised means here a ‘best case scenario’. We are aware that current funding streams, institutional, political, structural, time and other resource restrictions may make it difficult, or even impossible to follow this methodology to the core. Nevertheless, this outline should serve as a guideline for good practice. According to specific project conditions for creating the vision, adjustments may be necessary.

Based on our results we choose a methodology with intensive stakeholder engagement as its backbone. The stakeholder engagement process should be supported by research-based evidence, e.g. through assessments of the state of the art (e.g. environmental factors, economic realities, etc.). Indicators for these assessments can be fully or partially chosen by stakeholders.

Figure 1: Six working steps (blue) for creating an agroecological vision in a straight workflow, as supported by scientific evidence and assessments (yellow).

We identified six vital steps to guide the design of a vision creation process (Figure 1). All steps include stakeholder engagement to varying extent, yet the co-creation aspect is maintained throughout the process.

1. Problem identification

First, important food system stakeholder groups are mapped with support of gradually included actors and/or stakeholders (e.g. through interviews, surveys, or workshops). Thus, first stakeholder groups are preselected to give their input for identification of further stakeholder groups. Based on this mapping, different

homogeneous stakeholder groups separately outline their current situation ('is' state), using a holistic approach to identifying both elements that are going good (keepers) and concrete problem situations. The results will be fact checked according to existing scientific evidence or through targeted assessments, if no prior data exists. Then, the scientific feedback will be discussed with the stakeholder groups to refine their results.

In a second step, the earlier single-profile stakeholder groups will be brought together, thus mixing different interest spheres. In this step, the different stakeholder groups will discuss their individual results with the aim to define common problem situations that cover all stakeholder groups. While it may not be possible that all stakeholder groups acknowledge each other's identified problems, this step serves more to open up communication and to foster an environment of mutual exchange and understanding. Multiple perspectives will become apparent to the participants. Nonetheless, it is important that key problems that are identified within a specific stakeholder group are taken seriously in the following steps, irrespective of conflicts between the different groups.

2. Assessment of conditions

Together with the initial set of stakeholders, important forces, factors, internal and external processes that steer or affect the food system, and specific related processes are mapped. Lock-ins are identified that maintain or support the status quo and specific (additional) actors and actor groups are identified that may support the vision creation (e.g. politicians, community members, experts, NGOs, companies, etc.).

3. Method selection

Based on previous results, specific stakeholder engagement and vision creation methods are selected to address the actual vision co-creation. Here it is decided whether and/or when stakeholder groups should be engaged separately or together. Experiences of stakeholder engagement from previous steps will help with these decisions. The approach may differ between locations or nations in order to achieve best results according to specific conditions. Central for the method selection is the focus on how the identified food systems problems can be best addressed with regard to the vision creation and how facilitating factors can be integrated to their best use.

Methods should spark co-creators' imagination and creative potential in order to break out of established thought processes and to get into an imaginative space to create a desired future state. Storytelling and visualisation will be key elements of this process.

4. Vision co-creation

The selected methods are applied and the vision is co-created, covering short-term, mid-term, and long-term scales. Vision documents covering different scales (local, national, BSR) are created that describe the desired future state.

5. Reflection and adjustment

In iterative reflection cycles (number of iterations needs to be decided in step 3), the co-created visions from step 4 are compared with available scientific evidence, and previously identified content (stage 1 and 2). In co-creation and co-learning workshops, the visions will be further discussed, adjusted and verified.

6. Concretisation

Concrete steps for a holistic implementation of the vision on different levels (local, national, BSR) will be co-developed. The mapping of stage 2 can be utilised here. Implementation steps will be aligned along a timeline with short-term, mid-term and long-term actions.

'Seeds' (Pereira et al., 2018) - i.e. already existing activities, structures, legal frameworks, etc. - are identified that can be utilized for the vision implementation. These seeds are 'low hanging fruits' for getting the transformative process started and to demonstrate success. It is important to formulate strategies how each seed will be utilised in the process.

Creating an agroecological vision for the Baltic Sea Region requires that many different levels are addressed (i.e. local, national, and BSR). While this can be achieved in different ways, we propose to start locally, since stakeholders usually are most familiar and connected to their closer surroundings. Then the process can continue up the levels via national workshops to a Baltic Sea regional approach. This allows participants to get familiar with the topic, project goals and engagement processes, and participants for national and BSR level engagement can be selected. National and BSR level results can also build up on local results, thus helping to identify common problems and wishes at each level. For revising the visions (step 5), the levels can go backwards again from BSR via national to local level.

For the implementation of the vision(s), it is important to decide at which level the stewardship is taken for the diverse implementation steps (step 6). It is important that stakeholders and decision makers decide this, since they are the ones doing the implementation. Also, which implementation is promoted at which level will most likely differ between countries, although a general national support is desired. A BSR-level implementation board could also be a viable option to coordinate cross-national implementation efforts.

Overall, we found that a shared agroecological vision for the Baltic Sea Region is valuable and necessary for enabling systemic change and received very positive feedback among all engaged co-creators. The region's environmental challenges, socio-cultural ties, and emerging agroecological initiatives provide fertile ground for collective action. At the same time, success will depend on acknowledging and strategically addressing barriers, such as structural lock-ins, economic and political constraints. Stakeholder integration and co-creation seem to be both a requirement for success, but at the same time one of the biggest challenges. Therefore, sound stakeholder management and skilled facilitators are essential for a co-creation process at such a large scale.

A co-created BSR agroecological vision needs to be more than just a document. It must be a participatory process, a learning journey, and a strategic tool capable of aligning actors across borders and sectors. Through combining structured foresight, participatory design, creativity, political awareness, and evidence-based grounding, it is possible to generate a compelling, feasible, and publicly owned vision that unites the Baltic Sea Region through a living transition toward social, ecological, and economic sustainability.

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Appendix 1: Interview guide

Guide for semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders

target people / interviewees:

- key stakeholders who are acting in the topic cluster of AE

Goals of the key-stakeholder interviews are

- to support the development of a **follow-up project methodology** for creating a joint Baltic Sea region vision on agroecology.
- to allow for **early stage stakeholder engagement** for methodology and method design with regard to our follow-up project on developing an agroecological vision for impact. Stakeholders can influence the follow-up project development at an early stage, when major changes and adaptations to the methodology and project design are still possible.
- to **identify target groups** for stakeholder engagement during the follow-up project
- to undertake **preliminary mapping of agroecology** in the reviewed countries
- to **identify potential partners** for the follow-up project from all Baltic Sea neighboring countries

How we define Agroecology

Agroecology is an evolving paradigm pursuing just and sustainable food systems through integrating science, practice, and social movements. Emphasising the interconnectedness of ecological, social, economic, and political dimensions, agroecology aims at working with nature rather than against, while understanding human societies as an integrated part of their surrounding natural environment. As a science, it draws on transdisciplinary methodologies to understand and enhance the interactions between ecological processes, agricultural systems, economic, and socio-political contexts. In practice, agroecology prioritizes context-specific, place-based approaches that value biodiversity, soil health, ecological resilience, and traditional and indigenous knowledge for developing local food systems. As a social movement, it aligns with global struggles for food sovereignty, social equity, environmental rights and decolonization, advocating for systems of production and governance that challenge industrial agriculture's extractive and inequitable frameworks.

Rooted in the principles outlined by the HLPE (High Level Panel of Experts), the FAO's Ten Elements of Agroecology, and the Nyéléni Declaration, agroecology calls for systemic transformation of current food and knowledge systems. This transformation encompasses not only environmental dimensions—such as soil health, water conservation, and biodiversity—but also the economic, social, and political dimensions that shape how food systems function and for whom. Achieving an agroecological food system requires addressing these dimensions holistically, recognizing that sustainable change emerges from the intersection of ecological integrity, equitable economic practices, and political empowerment. Ultimately, agroecology's strength lies in its adaptability to diverse contexts, offering a pathway for communities to co-create sustainable, resilient, just, and self-determined food systems.

Agroecology is a way to build fair and sustainable food systems by combining science, farming methods, and community efforts. It focuses on working with nature, protecting biodiversity, improving soil health, and respecting traditional knowledge. Agroecology also looks at the connections between the environment, society, economy, and politics to create strong, local food systems. It calls for big

changes to replace harmful industrial farming with more balanced and fair ways of growing food, driven by local initiatives.

Comments:

- some similar questions may have been asked in previous projects
- clearly mark the important questions!

Guide for semi-structured interviews:

Icebreaker + background

We choose specific interviewees who work within the AE topic cluster. Their background information is known to some extent, so feel free to adapt the icebreaker and the interview specifically.

- Presenting ourselves:
We are working on the project **AE-Pro-Vision**, which stands for “Creating an Action Plan for an Agroecological Baltic Sea Region Vision”. It is funded by the Swedish Institute under the Baltic Sea Neighbourhood Programme. It’s a 16-months project, which brings together 5 partners from Sweden, Latvia, Lithuania, Denmark, and Finland, with an aim to pursue further cooperative effort across the Baltic Sea Region countries to set the ground for developing a joint Baltic Sea region vision for an agroecological transformation of our food systems. The ultimate goal of this ‘seed’ project is to develop a larger follow-up project on agroecology in this region. Therefore, we engage with key stakeholders in the Baltic Sea Region countries to identify main areas of interest and concern, develop a methodology for how to create an impactful vision, and prepare the ground for the follow-up project.
- Can you, please, briefly tell about **yourself** and the organisation(s) that you currently work for/represent?
- Have you been interviewed about AE previously? If yes, by whom?
This question aims at avoiding stakeholder fatigue due to previous interviews with similar questions. In case of previous interviews, we can specify the purpose of our approach and why we may ask similar questions (i.e. we need stakeholder specific information for this project in order to identify country/region specific details).

Definition and background of Agroecology in your country

- What does the term “agroecology” mean for you personally? How would you **define it**?
The different definitions by key stakeholders can be merged later to identify a first BSR specific definition of AE as an upstream stakeholder inclusive starting point for the follow-up project application.
- Do you feel that the way you define it differs in any ways from how it is understood and/or used in [your country] and/or in other countries? If so, what are the **main differences**?
- Have you observed any **recent changes** in the presence of the AE concept and the way AE is being featured in [your country]? If so, please elaborate! → would be interesting in a future project
- Short definition: In our project we define AE as a stakeholder inclusive and holistic problem solving pathway that relies on solutions that work together with nature rather than against it, while including people’s needs. In line with this definition AE is treated as a combination of science, practice, and social movement. Which of these **three dimensions** of AE (i.e. science/academic discipline, practice, movement/ philosophy) is more pronounced and which is less present in your country? In your opinion, why is it so?

- Are there **different terms** used by you personally or other stakeholders in [your country] that capture the same underlying ideas as AE in the way we define it?
It is worthwhile to collect such terms both in native languages and/or English. This can be helpful for future mapping activities and for finding suitable project partners.
- Keeping in mind the three AE dimensions (science/practice/movement/politics), how would you generally describe the **present state of AE in your country**?
- Is there a **community** developing around AE (or equivalent) concepts/approaches in your country?
If YES: who is contributing to the formation and development of such a network (initiatives, institutions, projects)? *Are there other initiatives?*
If NO: Which related initiatives, institutions, or projects do exist?
- What in your country is **boosting** the AE movement/development? (drivers: e.g. societal issues, policies, ect.)
- What in your country is **hindering** the AE movement/development? (roadblocks: e.g. societal issues, policies, ect.)

Methodology questions:

This section aims at getting key stakeholder input on how to develop a methodology for the follow-up project: how to create a joint Baltic Sea region vision on agroecology.

- How much do you think AE is known at the **national and/or BSR policy-making level** (who knows about it)? Have you observed any recent changes in that regard?
- We are aiming at developing an agroecological vision for the Baltic Sea Region. The purpose of the vision is to provide a joint goal for transformative action. What is **special about the BSR** regarding developing an AE Vision in the region?
- Do you see any **value in focusing on the BSR** when speaking about the future of AE?
 - o Which countries should be included in the BSR?
- If a joint BSR vision for AE is being developed, what should such a vision entail in terms of **goals and content (science, movement, practice, politics)**?
This is a key question, since it helps to form the content of the follow-up project. We can pick up replies as well during the following questions.
- Whom should the vision be **targeted at**? (Farmers, politicians, generally the food system, ...?)

- In your view, which **practical steps** would be needed to develop such a vision?
- **Who should be involved** in developing such a vision? Please mention specific stakeholder groups/organisations/individuals/industries!
- How would you describe the **current stakeholder interactions** within the agricultural/food sectors in your own country?
 - o Which stakeholder clusters exist?
 - o Which stakeholders are included/excluded?
 - o What are key paradigms? (industrial farming, re-naturation, consumer protests, ...)
- **How should people be involved** (what is a fair way that is still doable)?
 - o Is there a certain sequence in which specific actors/stakeholder groups need to be involved?
 - o Should there be a national deliberation first or should it focus on BSR from the start?

- What would **motivate** different stakeholders [in your country] to contribute to develop an AE vision?

- What do you perceive as potential **barriers and facilitating factors for developing such a vision?** (structural, institutional, cultural) How can they be addressed?

- Short: What's a good **time frame** for the vision? (implementation → what time span should the vision cover? i.e. 10 , 20, 50, 100, ... years)
- Are there other methodology elements that you think are important?

We can explain this question further. Purpose is to allow the interviewee to formulate any other suggestions or concerns they have with regard to developing the AE vision.

Ending questions:

- Would you **personally** be interested in contributing to developing such a joint AE vision for BSR?
- Can we contact you again for follow-up questions or other stakeholder events?

Appendix 2: Literature list

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